

IS ENES3 Data Request Review (September)

10th Sept, 4pm UK

To join by zoom:- <https://ukri.zoom.us/j/91321680336>
<https://ukri.zoom.us/j/3256908029>

Joined: Mich, Karl, Martin, Klaus, Alison, Matt, Paul

Apologies: Bryan (may join later)

Context

- Previous meetings: July:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wylSpCAzd3C5jFccpd0HGIEoQJsKAdnLW69hF5fg0EU/edit?usp=sharing> ; [20th May, 2020](#) (also <https://zenodo.org/record/3901310>).
- CMIP Data Request Roadmap ([Working document](#));
- Reference documents ([google sheet](#)).

Agenda

1. Discussion of variable prioritisation with CMIP Panel/WGCM: next steps.
 - The view from C3S (Martin)
 - Could engage with VIACSAB ...
 - Mich: we are not selling anything to C3S
 - List of variables: IPCC and C3S both looking for a subset; anything that is not in request?
 - Martin: no, no new requests; we (infrastructure providers) are selling our service providers
 - Paul: communicate with EGSF XC (Ghaleb Abdullah [chair] and lead of LLNL ESGF project, the 2021-2023 (LLNL ESGF) proposal aims to connect catalogues across DOE/LLNL, NASA, NOAA, very US-centric, but as these are being built out, why not connect with C3S?)

MICH: a discussion going on about WMO. res 67; heading into direction of using WMO system (WIS) used for NWP dissemination ... parts of CMIP could use this framework; would put CMIP into weather centres's core budget. WIS is behind ESGF in technology;
Paul: getting closer to making an operational data centre at LLNL ... still on short cycle funding .. but getting the idea.

Variable prioritisations:

Karl: think about DECK and historical, and prioritisation for those. There is talk of making CMIP7 more flexible not clear how this will be handled.

Klaus: was unclear to some how to deal with default priority vs. requested priority;

Mat: could demote everything;

Paul: DECK request ...

Paul: need to look at data storage cost of requests, and which ESGF node will be the MIP "home", and the CO2 emissions associated with the experiments of a MIP before the MIP and its experiments are approved by the CMIP panel

CMIP Panel is science focus, WIP has infrastructure perspective; was not (for CMIP6) much discussion of infrastructure requirements; need to think of justifications up front;

HighResMIP: could we get some standardised aggregated data? Martin: yes ... but how do we set the standards

Klaus: this is a social problem. Should we strive to involve more people early on; need to get people talking early on;

2. IS-ENES3 Milestone document on data request schema;

- Due this month
- Propose presenting an "architectural schema" (setting out packages, functions and responsibilities), rather than a detailed application schema.
- Advantages of exploiting ideas from the ISO 11179 standard on metadata registries.
- Action: Martin -- send round a document for review;
- Action: add a section on strategic view

3. Registry of (horizontal) grids.

- Useful first step might be to tackle vertical grids: list of available CMOR options is given here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Njhnp-rAhQNb9lo4d_0YFUOdPttcPpjQec4R_7BMUH8/edit#gid=1854910047; CDL fragments exist for most (perhaps all) in the CF convention.
- Set up a sub-group meeting? -- Paul, Klaus, Karl, Martin, Charlotte (need to discuss OM.P)
- Klaus: grid overlaps how do you deal with this → different approaches lead to confusion. (e.g. duplicated points with different values in one file).

Next meeting

October set up doodle for next meeting ... same time fo day.